

Updated deterministic transfer setup for 2D materials

Latest version of the setup introduced in:

Deterministic transfer of two-dimensional materials by all-dry viscoelastic stamping. Andres Castellanos-Gomez *et al* 2014 *2D Mater.* 1 011002

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Breadboard	Standa	1BS-2040-015	ferromagnetic steel	130.00 €
Sample and stamp stages + magnets	Amazon	LINK	20 magnets neodimium N52 square 10 x 10 x 4 mm	18.99 €
	Banggood	LINK	XYZ- 60x60mm stage	80.00 €
	Aliexpress	LINK	XY-Axis Precision Linear Stage Ball Bars Manual displacement Platform 60mmx60mm	45.00 €
	Thorlabs	MSRP01/M	Ø1.40" Manual Mini-Series Rotation Stage, Metric	66.53 €
Tube lens	Edmund Optics	#89-860	C-Mount Camera Adapter	60.00 €
	Edmund Optics	#89-871	1.0X Camera Tube	295.00 €
	Edmund Optics	#89-878	7X Zoom Module, Manual	750.00 €
	Edmund Optics	#89-888	Lower Module w/In-Line Illumination	275.00 €
	Edmund Optics	#89-903	4.0X Lower Lens	275.00 €
	Edmund Optics	#89-919	Fiber Optic Light Guide Adapter	125.00 €
	Edmund Optics	#89-920	Fiber Optic Light Guide Adapter to 10mm	55.00 €
Focusing	Aliexpress	LINK	Focusing stage coarse & fine	48.87 €
	Aliexpress	LINK	Ring adapter 50 mm to 76 mm	10.56 €
Post and mount	Thorlabs	RS300/M	Ø25.0 mm Pillar Post, M6 Taps, L = 300 mm, M4 Adapter Included	53.25 €
	Thorlabs	PB1	Mounting Post Base, Ø2.48" x 0.40" Thick	22.44 €
Screen	Amazon	LINK		89.90 €
Camera	Aliexpress	LINK	Camera HDMI	65.00 €
Light	Aliexpress	LINK	9 mm coaxial LED light	31.28 €

TOTAL 2 496.82 €

Motich metallurgical microscope
50x objective
18 MPix AMScope camera

Deterministic transfer system

Comparison between the image quality obtained with a standard metallurgical microscope, using a high magnification objective and a high-quality camera with the image obtained with the optics of the transfer setup.

Supplementing the sample stage with a heater:

In our original deterministic transfer recipe with Gel-Film we didn't need to heat up the sample but there are many other deterministic transfer technique that require control over the temperature of the sample. Motivated by this need we share the simple modification needed to supplement our deterministic transfer setup with a temperature stage for the sample.

HEATER LINK

Ceramic heater
20mm diam 24 V max

EPOXY GLUE LINK

Nural 26 epoxy

An inexpensive ceramic heater (less than 15 eur) is glued to the sample stage cylinder with epoxy glue.

The heater is connected to a TENMA power supply ([REF. 72-2705](#)) to bias the heater. Any benchtop power supply (even a 220V to 24V 2A power adaptor with a LED dimmer) would work. The benchtop power supply allows one to read both current and voltage which can be used to effectively calibrate the temperature of the heater for future operation without need to attach a temperature probe. Despite the low cost of the TENMA 72-2705 (100€) it allows to program it through USB connection which allows for further versatility.

